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The Impact of Government Regulations on Marketing Strategy Development: International Experience

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***Annotation:** Marketing is very important for the development of enterprises. Government regulation has a significant impact on the development of marketing strategies for companies around the world. The main aspects of this influence can be divided into several key areas, each of which affects the approaches and methods used in marketing strategies. In the following article, we will consider the normative documents of marketing not only in our country, but also in international experience, in Japan, Italy, China, the USA and European countries.*

***Key words:** Marketing, tax, marketing strategy, "marketing" departments, GDPR, e-commerce, SU Corporation.*

The main task of marketing is to identify the needs and requirements of each market, and to select those among them that the company can provide a higher level of service than other competitors. This allows the company to produce high-quality products and, as a result, increase the company's overall profit by satisfying the needs of consumers. The content and terminology of marketing are constantly updated, but they are associated with the process of exchange, the emergence of commodity-money relations, the development of sales forms, and the interaction of consumers with goods and services.

Market knowledge (comprehensive study of consumers, understanding their tastes and desires), market adaptation, and market influence are the basic principles of marketing.¹ The importance of marketing in sales is that today's companies and business campaigns are facing fierce competition that they have never experienced before. Many people are confused about the difference between marketing and sales. They are very different in meaning and implementation methods. Marketing is a systematic

¹ Nosirov P.; Abdullayeva L.; Marketing - the basis of a market economy, Tashkent, 1995.

project and theoretical concept that includes many areas. For example, market segmentation, target market selection, market offering, product, value and marketing planning, marketing programs are among them.

The influence of government regulations is of great importance in developing a marketing strategy. Government regulations (e.g. laws, decrees, resolutions, regulations) are the main regulatory documents regulating marketing activities and affect the following aspects:

1. Legal requirements. When developing a marketing strategy, companies need to take into account legal requirements established by the state. For example, there are requirements such as legal restrictions on advertising in certain areas, fair treatment of consumers, and non-distribution of falsified information. It is also necessary to prevent monopoly and pursue fair advertising and pricing policies to ensure competitiveness.
2. Taxes and government levies. Government tax policies also play an important role in developing a marketing strategy. Care must be taken in calculating and pricing government taxes correctly, as well as in choosing advertising and sales channels.
3. Certification of products and services. In some industries, certification of products or services by government agencies may be required. This creates the need to focus on certificates confirming the quality of the product when developing a marketing strategy.
4. Environmental and social responsibility. Government laws regarding environmental and social responsibility also affect marketing strategy. For example, issues such as developing environmentally friendly products, promoting social responsibility, and protecting consumers should be considered in marketing strategy.
5. International market and export laws. If a company plans to enter the international market, it is necessary to export and adapt to the requirements of international laws. This, in turn, requires taking into account international regulatory documents when developing a marketing strategy. Therefore, when developing a marketing strategy, it is important to take into account legal and economic restrictions based on state regulatory documents, as well as market regulatory factors. This will not only ensure the legality of marketing activities, but also increase the social and environmental responsibility of the brand.

When developing a marketing strategy, especially in the process of creating state regulatory documents, it is very important to study international experience. International experience and practices help to create good results and effective marketing strategies, taking into account the specific conditions of different countries. Marketing, as a theoretical concept and a specific phenomenon of commercial activity, was first used in the USA at the beginning of the 20th century², and the fact that it became the basis for initial marketing in this country, indicates the great experience of the United States in this area. The high concentration of production and capital, the dominance of monopolies in economic sectors, and the emergence of fierce competition in the international market objectively brought the problem of selling products to the forefront. In 1908, the first specialized firm studying marketing problems appeared in the United States. And in 1911, a number of large companies of that time opened the first departments engaged in commercial research. Companies began to establish "marketing" departments that were responsible for market research, advertising, customer service, and other management functions. In 1931, the American Marketing Society was founded, and in 1937, the American National Marketing Association. In the 1950s and 1960s, international marketing

² Jalolov J. J.; Marketing, Tashkent, 1999.

organizations such as the International Marketing Federation, the European Society for Public Opinion and Marketing, and the European Academy of Marketing were founded. Marketing is considered one of the modern professions.³

One of the most important parts of the influence of state regulations on the development of a marketing strategy in international practice is the understanding of regulations and legislation. At the international level, state regulations are often adapted to different economic, cultural, legal and political conditions. For example, in the European Union countries there are strict laws against advertising and marketing activities, which legally force companies to act with caution. International experience should be studied in the process of creating these laws.

International experience determines different procedures for brand and advertising activities. For example, in the USA, brands often create advertisements aimed at expanding consumer information, while in others, for example in Scandinavia, strategies that promote social and environmental responsibility prevail. Such norms determine how marketing should be carried out in the country.

International experience also shows that information and data protection play an important role in creating a marketing strategy. A number of countries, in particular European countries (for example, GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation), have strict laws on the protection of personal data of customers. Also, developed countries develop regulatory documents that ensure openness and transparency of data processing and use for advertising. When developing a marketing strategy, these laws and procedures should be studied.

Social responsibility and sustainability also play an important role in international experience. Many countries require social responsibility to be taken into account in marketing strategies. This includes environmental sustainability, social justice and the protection of consumer rights. International experience helps to include best practices in these areas when developing state regulatory documents.

Taking into account digital marketing and technologies also plays an important role in international marketing strategy. International marketing strategy, especially digital marketing, may differ between countries. For example, in Singapore and China, interest in digital advertising and e-commerce is very high, while in developing countries this area is not yet fully developed. Therefore, when introducing digital marketing into state regulations, it is necessary to analyze it based on international experience.

Japanese marketing strategy and tactics are characterized by the use of trading companies as agents for the sale of goods. Trading companies take on all intermediary functions associated with commercial affairs. They perform such tasks as currency calculations, tariffs, freight forwarding and quotas. They operate taking into account all the difficulties associated with the sale of goods in local markets, as well as the political, economic, scientific, territorial characteristics of regions and countries.

Each trading company is engaged in the sale of products manufactured by several firms at the same time. In this case, it receives a high commission (up to 30% of net income). The Japanese department of the SU Corporation was specially organized to help Japanese intermediary firms sell products. The diagram below shows the organizational structure of this department. As shown in the diagram, in the regional marketing department, marketing functions (tasks) are distributed between the sales and support departments. Employees of the sales department are responsible for the implementation of sales plans in certain regions of Japan for months, quarters and the whole year. They achieve this task by supporting the sales representatives of the intermediary firm.

³ Jalolov J. J.; Marketing, Tashkent, 1999.

In conclusion, it can be said that when developing state regulations, it is necessary to study international experience, take into account innovative approaches, social responsibility, legal procedures and effective methods of marketing. This will help to achieve success not only in the domestic market, but also on a global scale.

References:

1. Nosirov P.; Abdullayeva L.; Marketing - the basis of a market economy, Tashkent, 1995.
2. Jalolov J. J.; Marketing, Tashkent, 1999.
3. Golbukov E.P., Golbukova E.N., Sekerin V.D. Marketing: Choosing the best solution. - M.: Economica, 2009. 93-97- pp.
4. Overchuk, L. Macromarketing regulation of the US food market / L. Overchuk // Int. agricultural journal. 2005. No. 6.
5. Countries and regions of the world: economic and political reference / edited by A. S. Bulatov. Moscow: Prospect, 2005.